

EFFECTS OF RADIATION EXPOSURE IN CHRONIC DISEASES

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Annotation: Radiation danger is not a myth, but a real problem that is relevant for any person. Every year there are new inventions and technologies that are both beneficial and harmful to humanity. In modern conditions, the radiation background constantly fluctuates, and even if the excess of permissible norms is insignificant, it can adversely affect the state of health and general well-being.

Keywords: radioactive substances, pathology develops

Radiation particles tend to accumulate in organs and tissues, increasing the risk of developing dangerous diseases. Even if you use only natural products, drink water from your own well, you still cannot guarantee yourself and your loved ones absolute protection from radiation. Its particles easily penetrate into drinking water, vegetables and fruits, even if they are from your own garden. There is a huge amount of radium in the bowels of the earth, the half-life of which lasts

hundreds of years. There are other potentially dangerous elements that can get into your body together with water and food.

Man is not protected by nature from radiation. It has no mechanisms capable of detecting and perceiving ionizing radiation. It is generally accepted in society that it is possible to obtain an excess of radioactive substances only while working at nuclear power plants, reactors and other secret facilities. Few people realize that a new fur coat, an expensive painting or a rare TV set that came from my grandmother can be sources of radiation and emit harmful substances for decades. And you will not find out about it right away, and even when indirect signs of the disease appear, you will most likely blame them on fatigue, overwork or habitual lack of sleep.

Unlike medications taken or toxic substances that enter the body together with food, radioactive substances are not simply excreted - they gradually accumulate. And this is a delayed-action mechanism, which sooner or later may require a long and expensive restoration of health.

Fissile radionuclides can enter the human body by external and internal irradiation. External influences are atmospheric air, as well as various environmental objects that may contain radioactive substances. Internal radiation occurs after a person eats contaminated food, water, air masses entering the bronchi and lungs.

Many building materials have radioactivity. Natural stone, concrete, limestone are used for the construction of buildings, decorative decoration, and few people know that they are radioactive. The main source of natural radiation is radon, which is formed during the decay of radium. This gas is often found in residential and

basement rooms, it is present in water and food. In order to prevent the accumulation of radon in the room, it is necessary to ventilate the rooms more often and responsibly approach the choice of building materials for the construction of residential buildings. High-quality ventilation systems should be installed in the basements, which will prevent the accumulation of radioactive radon gas.

Most of the radionuclides formed as a result of nuclear weapons testing fall out in the form of radioactive fallout. Rainwater penetrates into the ground, gets into vegetables and fruits, groundwater and follows on, sooner or later reaching the human body, where radioactive substances slowly accumulate, causing common diseases, the most dangerous of which are considered malignant neoplasms. Millions of people in the world are diagnosed with cancer every year, which is closely related to radiation.

Radiation sickness is the result of the influence of increased doses of radiation on the cells of the body. This disease develops when the radiation exceeds the maximum permissible values. Radiation sickness affects absolutely all body systems.

For a long time it was believed that pathology develops only with simultaneous intensive irradiation. But then it was found that radioactive substances have the ability to accumulate, so the disease can also occur as a result of prolonged exposure to radiation, when a person has been working in harmful production for many years or lives in an area that has an unfavorable radiation background.

The damaging factors in radiation sickness can be X-rays, alpha and beta particles, gamma rays, possibly a combination of different types of radioactive radiation. First of all, radiation exposure affects cells that differ in active division. These are the endocrine glands, bone marrow, lymphoid tissue, neurons. The key feature of radiation sickness is the absence of any sensations of radiation damage. A person begins to understand that he got into the zone of a radioactive field, not immediately, but only after the appearance of characteristic signs of the disease.

Characteristic signs of the chronic form are:

weight loss;

loss of appetite;

reproductive disorders;

menstrual cycle failure;

reduction of libido up to impotence;

chronic abdominal and stomach pain;

insomnia;

decline of strength;

frequent respiratory viral diseases.

An acute form of radiation sickness requires hospitalization of the patient. The patient is placed in sterile conditions, where the rules of infectious safety are strictly observed. The patient needs bed rest, rest and professional care. Specialists

carry out primary surgical treatment of wounds; take active actions to prevent infectious complications. The use of drugs that neutralize the effect of specific radioactive substances is shown. Special attention is paid to detoxification, since the body suffers greatly from toxic substances during radiation sickness.

Literatures:

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